

Apparent Molar Volume of Uniunivalent Salts in Dioxane + Water Mixtures

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Apparent molar volumes of univalent (Ten) salts have been studied in dioxane + water mixtures at 10, 20 and 30% (by wt.) within the temperature range 30–45° and ion-solvent interaction has been inferred.

ION-solvent interaction studies have attracted considerable attraction in recent years¹. The influence of the interaction is derived from molar volume as it can be easily calculated from the density data. The apparent molar volume of KCl, KBr, KNO₃, KIO₃, NaCl, NaBr, NaNO₃, NaBrO₃ and NaIO₃ in dioxane + water mixture at 10, 20 and 30% (by wt.) have been studied in the temperature range 30–45° and the nature of ion-solvent interaction has been derived.

Experimental

All the salts used were of 'extra pure' (E. Merck) grade. The procedures for preparation of the solvents and solutions were the same as before¹. The buoyancy correction has been considered for density measurements. Measures were taken to check evaporation of the solvent. Density readings were precise upto 0.0002 g cm⁻³. The concentration range was 0.1–0.001 mol dm⁻³.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v°) has been calculated from the density data of the solution using equation(1),

$$\phi_v = \frac{M}{\rho_o} - \left(\frac{\rho - \rho_o}{\rho_o} \right) \frac{10^3}{C} \quad (1)$$

where, the terms have their usual significance. The data obtained have been found to agree with the Masson equation²,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^\circ + S_v C^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

as the plot of ϕ_v vs $C^{1/2}$ is linear. The values of the limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v°) obtained from the extrapolation of the plot to zero concentration are presented in Table 1 and the slope (S_v) has been found to be positive (data not given).

Dependence of ϕ_v° on temperature : It is evident from Table 1 that ϕ_v° increases with the increase in temperature for all the ten salts in dioxane + water mixtures. This increase can be explained on the basis of primary and secondary solvation layers

Dioxane wt. % Temp. °C	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%
	KCl			NaCl		
30	17.2	15.8	13.3	25.2	24.1	22.1
35	17.3	16.4	14.4	25.4	24.3	22.4
40	17.4	16.6	14.6	25.5	24.4	22.6
45	17.9	16.8	14.9	25.9	24.5	22.7
	KBr			NaBr		
30	21.1	23.6	24.1	31.5	32.2	33.3
35	22.2	23.9	24.3	32.1	33.1	33.4
40	22.5	24.4	24.6	32.9	33.3	34.7
45	23.3	24.8	25.0	33.0	33.5	35.6
	KNO ₃			NaNO ₃		
30	24.5	25.8	28.9	30.7	32.6	35.9
35	27.2	29.4	31.3	35.7	37.5	40.9
40	32.5	34.4	35.2	40.6	41.5	45.5
45	36.3	38.8	40.4	41.8	43.4	48.1
	KBrO ₃			NaBrO ₃		
30	132.0	138.8	145.6	109.8	115.4	120.8
35	135.3	140.4	147.0	111.2	116.5	121.2
40	137.2	142.5	148.8	112.4	117.0	121.2
45	138.4	143.8	150.6	113.5	118.8	122.0
	KIO ₃			NaIO ₃		
30	166.3	169.4	174.5	130.5	133.0	137.1
35	170.0	173.4	178.0	132.2	135.3	139.0
40	172.8	176.4	182.0	134.2	137.9	141.0
45	175.8	179.0	183.9	135.5	139.6	142.4

which appear to be formed around the ion³. At higher temperature the solvent from the secondary solvation layers is released to the bulk resulting in the expansion of the solution rapidly than the pure solvent⁴.

Limiting slope (S_v) : At all the temperatures studied the limiting apparent slope (S_v) of the Masson equation is positive (data not given) suggesting ion-ion interaction. This increases with the increase in dioxane content. This is attributed to the change in the mobility of the ions due to the change in the dielectric constant and is found to be in the order, IO₃⁻ > BrO₃⁻ > Cl⁻ > Br⁻ > NO₃⁻, for both K⁺ and Na⁺.

Dependence of ϕ_v° on dioxane : It is interesting to note that ϕ_v° increases with the increase in dioxane

TABLE 2— $\bar{V}_{ion}$ OF UNIUNIVALENT SALTS ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) AT 40°

Ion	Crystallographic radii	10%	20%	30%	Ion	Crystallographic radii	10%	20%	30%
Cl ⁻	1.81	9.5	14.3	14.55	Cl ⁻	1.81	3.4	10.6	9.6
Br ⁻	1.95	16.76	23.26	26.69	Br ⁻	1.95	8.5	18.4	18.5
NO ₃ ⁻	2.05	24.58	31.48	33.48	NO ₃ ⁻	2.03	18.5	28.4	30.2
BrO ₃ ⁻	2.50	121.2	132.5	140.8	BrO ₃ ⁻	3.20	98.4	111.0	116.2
IO ₃ ⁻	3.2	156.8	165.4	174.0	IO ₃ ⁻	3.50	120.2	131.9	136.0
K ⁺	1.39	18.9	10.0	7.85	Na ⁺	0.95	14.4	5.8	8.8

content for all the salts excepting Cl⁻. This may be ascribed to the low surface charge density as a result of which electrostatic attraction is more in a medium of low dielectric constant, and hence ion-solvent interaction would also be more and consequently ϕ_v^0 will be larger¹. The ion-solvent interaction order is $\text{IO}_3^- > \text{BrO}_3^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$.

Partial ionic volume: From the ϕ_v^0 values, partial ionic volumes of common ions have been used to investigate the nature of the ion-solvent interaction. For the sake of convenience, it is assumed that $\phi_v^0 \equiv \bar{V}^0$ for different salts. Only the data at 40° is given for illustration. It is assumed that the additivity law holds good for $\bar{V}^0$ for electrolytes in dioxane+water mixtures. $\bar{V}^0$ of the salts have been divided into ionic contributions by plotting $\bar{V}^0$ vs r^3 assuming that for the spherical ions, $\bar{V}^0$ should be a monotonic function of the crystal radii. It is found that $\bar{V}^0$ anion are different for different cations like K⁺ and Na⁺ (Table 2).

The limiting partial molar volume of an ion may be assumed to be the sum of two major contributions, namely, the geometric part and the electrostriction part⁵ and can be written as

$$\bar{V}_{ion}^0 = \bar{V}_{geom}^0 + \bar{V}_{elec}^0 \quad (3)$$

where, $\bar{V}_{geom}^0$ takes into account the intrinsic volumes of ions plus the void space effects created on introducing the ions in the solvent, and $\bar{V}_{elec}^0$, the contribution due to electrostriction is due to the electrostatic ion-dipole interaction. A number of relations have been proposed connecting these two effects with the radius of the ions^{5,6},

$$\bar{V}_{ion}^0 = Ar^3 - B \frac{Z^2}{r} \quad (4)$$

$$\bar{V}_{ion}^0 = 2.52 r^3 + (A - 2.52) r^3 - B \frac{Z^2}{r} \quad (5)$$

Equations (4) and (5) have been used to separate the geometric and electrostriction part as the plot of $\bar{V}^0/r/z^2$ vs r^4/z^2 is linear. The constant B , the electrostriction part, is obtained from the intercept, and A , the geometric part, is obtained from the slope. These values are found to be different when paired with K⁺ and Na⁺. The electrostriction due to electrostatic ion-solvent interaction increases with the increase in dioxane content in case of anions

when paired with K⁺, whereas it is reversed when paired with Na⁺ (Table 3).

 TABLE 3—CONSTANTS A AND B IN EQUATION (4) AT 40°

	Dioxane wt %	A $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	B $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$
When paired with K ⁺	10	616	10.00
	20	623	12.20
	30	550	14.40
When paired with Na ⁺	10	3.95	18.5
	20	3.66	14.4
	30	4.16	11.2

The geometric part of the partial molar volume has further been divided into the intrinsic size of the ion, $\bar{V}_{int}^0$ and the void space effect $\bar{V}_{disorder}^0$ using equation (5). The disorderlines is found to be more in case of ions when paired with K⁺ than when paired with Na⁺ (Table 4). So it is concluded that the partial molar volumes of anions are dependent on the cation with which they are paired.

 TABLE 4— $\bar{V}_{disorder}^0$ AT 40°

Dioxane wt %	When paired with K ⁺ ($A = 2.52$) $r^3 \text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$						
	K	Cl ⁻	Br ⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	BrO ₃ ⁻	IO ₃ ⁻	
10	9.79	21.50	28.00	30.47	56.86	119.26	
20	10.02	22.04	28.57	31.09	57.99	121.53	
30	8.02	17.67	22.11	24.94	46.55	97.62	
	When paired with Na ⁺						
	10	1.24	8.49	10.63	11.98	22.35	46.86
	20	0.98	6.76	8.46	9.54	17.81	37.35
30	1.43	9.74	12.19	13.74	25.63	53.74	

This behaviour can be explained as follows. Dioxane is more basic and less acidic than water because of the electron-releasing tendency of the methylene groups in the molecules. A water molecule which is hydrogen-bonded to the oxygen atom of a dioxane molecule also becomes more basic and less acidic than pure water. A cation will interact more strongly with the oxygen atom of dioxane+water mixtures. An anion will interact less strongly with the hydrogen atoms. This type of ion-solvent interaction is in the primary solvation sheath. Hence the behaviour of Na⁺ will be different from that of K⁺, as has been found.

References

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